

The effect of exploration speed on vibratory signals in haptic perception of materials

Anna Metzger¹[0000-0002-5704-2821] and Matteo Toscani¹[0000-0002-1884-5533]

Bournemouth University, BH12 5BB, Poole, United Kingdom
ametzger@bournemouth.ac.uk
<https://bournemouthperceptionlab.co.uk/>

Abstract. We are excellent at haptically identifying different materials primarily based on vibrations elicited on the skin during their exploration. These signals depend on exploration speed as they mirror in time the spatial structure of the material's surface. However, our material perception is speed invariant. We recently have shown that vibratory signals can be approximated by a single parameter in the temporal frequency domain (slope), which varies systematically between material categories and correlates with human perceptual judgements. Here we tested how this parameter changes with different exploration speed. In our experiment participants explored 74 material samples from 7 different material categories using a tool and different exploration speed while we recorded vibratory signals elicited by the interaction. Consistent with our previous findings, the slope significantly differed between material categories. However, it didn't significantly change across different exploration speeds. Furthermore, slope variability was correlated with consistency of perceptual ratings across different speed levels. Our results suggest that extracting the slope in the temporal frequency domain is a potential mechanism for speed invariance in haptic perception of materials.

Keywords: Material · Perception · Exploration · Vibration · Speed

1 Introduction

We are extremely good at recognizing which material an object is made of by touch. Identification of the material an object is made of is crucial to interact with it. For instance, we need to be more careful with a glass made of glass than the one made of plastic. Haptic perception of materials is based on the dynamic contact between the hand and the material's surface (lateral movement across the object's surface, [1]), translating the spatial structure of its surface into a vibration on the skin [2, 3]. Crucially, the same material could give rise to dramatically different vibratory signals when exploration speed changes. Nevertheless, we can recognize materials across different exploration speeds, suggesting that haptic perception of materials is speed invariant. Indeed, populations of neurons in the somatosensory cortex exhibit some degree of speed constancy (SC) [4], indicating that SC computations are performed at some processing stage. In principle SC could also be achieved by normalizing neural responses by movement speed, however, SC is found also when textures are passively scanned [5] (i.e. a measure of movement speed is not available). How SC is achieved in haptic perception of objects is yet an open question.

In previous research, exploratory speed was not systematically varied or existing measures of SC in humans only involved a limited set of materials [6]. We previously argued that the relative frequency composition of vibrations elicited by the exploration of natural textures follows a $\frac{1}{f^s}$ Fourier amplitude spectrum, with s being the slope characterizing this relationship, which is linear in log-log space [7]. We showed that s systematically varies between material categories and correlates with human perceptual judgements. This parameter is a measure of relative spectral composition: steep slope indicates dominance of low spatial frequency; shallow slope indicates dominance of high spatial frequencies. Being a relative measure and reflecting human perceptual judgments [7], this parameter may exhibit a certain degree of speed invariance therefore, being a natural candidate for SC. If perceptual representations are based on slope and slope speed invariance explains SC, we expect that SC performance is proportionally related to how much slope changes between different exploratory speeds for different materials.

2 Results & Discussion

Participants (N=4) explored 74 material samples (prepared as in [7]) from 7 material categories (fabric, metal, animal, wood, paper, stone and plastic) with a tool (3D printed pen as in [3, 7]) and without vision of them and their exploring hand and with audio being covered by white noise, while we were recording vibratory signals elicited by the exploration (via a accelerometer ADXL345 mounted on the pen, at 3200Hz). Figure 1A shows that participants could be trained to implement different exploration speed (slow, medium, fast) with the help of online visual feedback (displayed on a monitor) of their speed, based on motion tracking of their palm midpoint via Ultra-leap stereo IR 170 (at 90Hz). Further, it can be seen that experimental speed manipulations were both below and above the natural speed (free) spontaneously used by participants without feedback.

Fig. 1. A) Average performed exploration speed as a function of instructed speed level. B) Slope in the temporal frequency domain for each material category and speed level. C) Rating consistency as a function of slope variability.

Vibratory signals were processed as in [7]. Figure 1B shows the average slope s in the temporal frequency domain as a function of speed condition and material category. The 7(material category) \times 4(exploration speed) repeated measures ANOVA revealed a significant effect of material category, $F(6,18) = 136.26$, $p < 0.001$, $\eta^2 = 0.9$, while the effect of speed was not significant, $F(1.11,3.32) = 2.89$, $p = 0.181$ (Greenhouse-Geisser corrected), $\eta^2 = 0.01$, confirming that s systematically varied between material categories while it was rather similar across different exploration speed within a material category. The significant interaction between material category and speed, $F(18,54) = 8.89$, $p < 0.001$, $\eta^2 = 0.04$, indicates that s differs across different speed more for some material category than another. However, it is clear from the effect sizes that material category explained most of the variability in s .

After the exploration participant reported how each material felt according to 7 adjective pairs (hard vs. soft, high friction vs. slippery, orderly vs. chaotic, rough vs. smooth, textured/patterned vs. homogeneous/uniform, elastic vs. not elastic and warm vs. cold). If slope is used by the perceptual system to achieve SC, we could expect that materials for which slope changes less across different speed levels will exhibit higher SC. Indeed, SC, assessed as rating consistency, i.e. the correlation between perceptual ratings across the 3 different experimental speed levels was significantly correlated with slope variability across speed levels for each material sample and averaged across participants $t(72) = -2.01$, $p < 0.05$ (Fig. 1C).

Overall, our results suggest that the slope in the temporal frequency domain is a potential mechanism to achieve speed constancy.

Acknowledgments. The research was supported by the The Leverhulme Trust through the British Academy/Leverhulme Small Research Grants Scheme (SRG2324\240793).

Disclosure of Interests. The authors have no competing interests to declare.

References

1. Lederman, S. J., Klatzky, R. L.: Hand movements: A window into haptic object recognition. *Cognitive psychology*, **19**(3), 342–368 (1987)
2. Weber, A. I., Saal, H. P., Lieber, J. D., Cheng, J. W., Manfredi, L. R., Dammann III, J. F., Bensmaia, S. J.: Spatial and temporal codes mediate the tactile perception of natural textures. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, **110**(42), 17107-17112 (2013)
3. Metzger, A., Toscani, M.: Unsupervised learning of haptic material properties. *Elife* **11**: e64876 (2022)
4. Lieber, J. D., Bensmaia, S. J.: Emergence of an invariant representation of texture in primate somatosensory cortex. *Cerebral Cortex*, **30**(5), 3228-3239 (2020)
5. Bensmaia, S. J., Hollins, M.: The vibrations of texture. *Somatosensory & motor research*, **20**(1), 33-43 (2003).
6. Boundy-Singer, Z. M., Saal, H. P., Bensmaia, S. J.: Speed invariance of tactile texture perception. *Journal of neurophysiology*, **118**(4), 2371-2377 (2017)
7. Toscani, M., Metzger, A.: A database of vibratory signals from free haptic exploration of natural material textures and perceptual judgments (viper): analysis of spectral statistics. In: Seifi, H., et al. *Haptics: Science, Technology, Applications. EuroHaptics 2022. Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, vol 13235. pp. pp. 319-327. Springer, Cham. (2022)